

PREPRINT

Developing a Robotic Hybrid Network for Coastal Surveillance: the INFORE Experience

Gabriele Ferri¹, Raffaele Grasso¹, Elena Camossi¹, Alessandro Faggiani¹,
Konstantina Bereta², Marios Voudas², Dimitris Kladis², Dimitris Zissis², Kevin D. LePage¹

Abstract

INFORE EU H2020 project has the objective of developing a real-time, interactive extreme-scale analytics and forecasting system capable of handling and analysing massive data streams. The system is validated in three different real-world use cases, In this paper we describe one of them, presenting the development of the INFORE system for a coastal surveillance Maritime Situational Awareness (MSA) application. The MSA INFORE system exploits the synergy between global view (AIS data, ESA Sentinel satellite data), providing contextual information over a wider area, and local view produced by a sensorised hybrid robotic network. The network is composed of an RGB/thermal camera onshore and of two Wave Gliders robots equipped with passive sonars. We focus on the development of this network, describing the cooperative autonomy framework to control the robots. The framework enables the robots to make decisions on their navigation for improving vessel detection and tracking. The INFORE MSA network demonstrates the benefits that the synergy between machine learning, AI and autonomous robots can bring in this kind of monitoring systems. The developed autonomy strategies increase the quality of the information produced by robots. These high-quality real-time observations are fused with the global view in the INFORE MSA and decision-support platform. Data fusion from multi-modal data sources results crucial for the detection of complex events (e.g. illegal fishing), which can then be communicated to decision-makers. Different modules of the systems are ready and under testing. The whole system will be validated in a trial in 2022.

Index Terms

MSA, coastal surveillance, cooperative autonomy, Wave Glider, Autonomous Surface Vehicles (ASVs), robotic networks

I. INTRODUCTION

The Maritime Situational Awareness (MSA) is the capability of understanding events, circumstances and activities impacting the maritime environment [1]. This is achieved through an effective Situational Assessment, which is the process that seamlessly condenses the acquisition of information from the real world, its interpretation to understand the ongoing situation and the projection into the future to support decision making.

The improvement of MSA is therefore vital for many important maritime scenarios, such as coastal monitoring and maritime security applications, which are addressed in this paper. These applications are traditionally conducted by means of manned vessels, sensors placed on-shore, such as radars and, more recently, using remote sensing from space [2]. The development of advanced monitoring platforms, composed of a multitude of data sources, imposes that the systems are capable of handling massive data flows streaming from multiple sources, of fusing the received information with the objective of producing significant event notifications. For achieving this, a variety of approaches can be used like machine learning, signal processing, statistical analysis and rule-based approaches. The objective is to analyse historical and real-time data to generate meaningful information and future forecasts for the decision-maker. For instance, in a maritime security applications, the monitoring system has to be capable to raise alarms in case of anomalous ship behaviours, reducing the false alarms and providing valid information both from the content and time perspective. The system operator is then called to verify and closely inspect the alarms. Typically, this happens by means of a manned vessel approaching the suspect ship for the final investigation. An effective and fast analysis of the real-time streams and historical data is therefore crucial to notify significant alarms and to forecast possible situations of interest.

To this aim, MSA can highly benefit from recent advances in marine robotics [3]–[5], which suggest that Maritime Unmanned Systems (MUS) can offer novel approaches to many scenarios such as coastal surveillance [6]. MUS are characterised by lower sensing, computational and communication capabilities if compared to traditional assets. However, they can build intelligent networks to accomplish complex missions with features of reliability, persistence, scalability and adaptability [6], [7]. Such robotic networks can complement fixed sensors and remote sensing providing persistent monitoring of an area [8]. Furthermore, they can relieve the system operators activity. Robots can move, upon indication either of an automatic system or of the operator

This work has been supported by the INFORE EU H2020 project, grant agreement No 825070.

¹NATO STO Centre for Maritime Research and Experimentation (CMRE), Viale San Bartolomeo 400, 19126 La Spezia (SP), Italy
Gabriele.Ferri@cmre.nato.int.

²Marine Traffic, Katekachi 75, 32 Vassar Street Athens, 115 25, Greece.

himself, to produce an improved and persistent local view. This can greatly increase the maritime situational awareness, hence dramatically reducing false alarms. The operator would use expensive means (the manned vessels) only in the few cases in which this is really needed.

In this paper we describe the research carried out in the framework of the Interactive Extreme-Scale Analytics and Forecasting (INFORE) EU H2020 project [9], aiming at the development of an advanced robotics-based MSA system for a coastal surveillance application.

INFORE started in 2019 with the objectives of developing a real-time, interactive extreme-scale analytics and forecasting system capable of handling and analysing massive data streams [9]. INFORE aims at developing a flexible, pluggable, distributed software architecture that is programmable and set up by graphical data processing workflows and that will be validated in three different use cases from the life sciences, financial and maritime domains.

For the maritime use case described in this paper, the INFORE approach is declined to develop a system addressing the requirements for a modern and effective surveillance application. The NATO STO-Centre for Maritime Research and Experimentation (CMRE), together with Marine Traffic and NCSR Demokritos, have been developing an integrated platform for coastal surveillance at the intersection of advanced robotics, remote sensing, machine learning and big data. The system relies on the management, fusion and analysis of massive data streams coming from multiple heterogeneous sources, such as remote sensing, fixed sensors onshore and mobile robotics nodes. Marine Traffic and NCSR Demokritos are leading the analysis and interpretation of the *global view* sensor data, such as Automatic Identification System (AIS) and Sentinel satellites Multi-Spectral Instrument (MSI) and Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) measurements [10], while CMRE has been developing a robotic *hybrid* network [8], composed of fixed and mobile sensors, the robots. The network is composed of an onshore thermal and RGB camera, and of two Liquid Robotics Wave Gliders autonomous surface vehicles, equipped with passive sonar sensors [11]–[13]. Wave Gliders have the advantages of emitting low noise during their navigation and are difficult to detect by radar/optical sensors. The robotics network produces the so-called *local view*. Global and local views are fused and interpreted by the INFORE system to enable a Complex Event detector to raise meaningful alarms for the decision-maker. This can potentially trigger the movement of a fast autonomous vessel (or a flying drone) for the final alarm confirmation.

A novel aspect of the proposed approach is the exploitation by the system of the robotic nodes mobility to improve the information produced by the local view sensors. To achieve this, the "intelligence" has been brought onboard the robots to enable cooperative decision-making on the basis of the current situation [13]–[15]. In a typical scenario, the INFORE system triggers and calls the robots to a certain area of interest on the basis of the global view measurements, for instance to investigate one suspicious vessel that has turned its AIS transponder off. The robots navigate towards that region for detecting the target by their passive sonar sensors [13]. Cooperative autonomy strategies based on Occupancy Grid Mapping [13], [14] have been developed to this purpose. Robots share information to estimate the target position and cooperatively move to improve the vessel detection and tracking. Then, they will start sending target-related information to the INFORE system which will use them for complex event detection, such as to detect a particular forbidden behaviour of the vessel.

The INFORE MSA network demonstrates the benefits that the synergy between machine learning, AI and autonomous robots can bring in this kind of monitoring systems. The virtuous circle between cooperative autonomy, data fusion and decision-making is evident. System decisions trigger the robot autonomy, hence controlling the vehicles for improving the effectiveness of data collection and fusion. The higher information quality produced increases the situational awareness. This allows the system to control the robot fleet more effectively. The final result is the improvement of the local view, leading to a better support for the final end-user decision-making.

In the following, after providing an overview of the INFORE MSA system, we will focus on the development and operations of the hybrid robotics network.

II. INFORE MSA SYSTEM OVERVIEW

In Fig. 1 is reported a sketch of the INFORE system. It is composed of a set of global view sensors which observe a wide area and provide contextual information. The system is composed of:

- A set of sensors for the global view to observe a wider area and provide contextual information.
- A hybrid network of dynamic and static sensor for the local view that provides real-time observations in a limited area of interest of cooperative as well as non-cooperative targets.
- A platform for situational awareness and decision-making. The platform integrates data and information streams from the local and global view sensors and analyses the behaviour of single surface targets as well as of the global vessel traffic surrounding them.

Global view is provided by Sentinel satellites MultiSpectral Instrument (MSI) and SAR data [10] and AIS streams transmitted by the vessels [16]. AIS messages are transmitted by each ship and contain her unique identifier, position and speed, and her current navigational status. The INFORE MSA and decision-support platform processes the data flows coming from the cooperative AIS sensor and those from non-cooperative sensors (MSI and SAR). It correlates them with historical data about

Fig. 1. INFORE system overview. Global view sensors are Sentinel satellite data, AIS data transmitted by the ships. Local view is created by a hybrid network composed of autonomous, cooperative Wave Glider surface robots and an onshore thermal/RGB camera. Data flows are transmitted to the INFORE MSA and decision-support platform that relies on machine learning and historical data to support the system C2 centre.

Fig. 2. Workflow of the maritime situational awareness INFORE maritime use case. The different data flows are fused together with historical data to detect simple and complex events. Examples of simple events are proximity events, while possible complex events are fishing in not allowed areas or piracy acts. All events produced by the INFORE workflow, are finally visualised using the UI of the MSA application

vessel routes (e.g. common patterns of ships travelling from one port to another) in order to identify possible events and raise alarms respectively.

The aforementioned sources are provided as input to the fusion engine of the INFORE platform. The fusion of global and local view heterogeneous streams of data plays a significant role in acquiring a complete picture of the maritime domain. The FUSION engine is an Akka¹-based distributed system that is provided to the INFORE platform as service that fuses different kinds of maritime data efficiently. The different streams of data are provided as input to the fusion engine using the Kafka (<https://kafka.apache.org>) framework, i.e., each data source corresponds to a different Kafka topic that is provided as input to the INFORE platform. The output of the fusion engine is a set of vessel trajectories deriving from multiple sources of maritime data as described above. However, being able to process and derive knowledge from large volumes of trajectory data coming from different sources is very challenging. To be able to address the scalability issues that come with the processing of big amounts of maritime data, we use the synopsis data engine of INFORE (SDE) [17]. The SDE component takes as input large amounts of data and creates synopses, i.e., lightweight representative data summaries in order to facilitate data processing with minimal loss of accuracy. In the MSA use case, the SDE creates synopses of trajectory data, i.e., simplified trajectories that contain reduced number of points without affecting the accuracy of the data science tasks that operate on them.

The simplified trajectories are then forwarded to the Maritime Event Detector [18], [19]. The maritime event detector is a component that is executed on a distributed fashion and it is deployed on a MarineTraffic Akka cluster. The Maritime Event Detector performs analysis on the trajectories and derives events. An example of such an event is the AIS-off event that occurs when a vessel stops transmitting AIS messages. Another example is the proximity event, which occurs when two vessels get very close to each other, which might be an indicator for a collision or a transshipment between the vessels in proximity. Then, simple events can be used to extract more complex events, using the Complex Event Processing/Event component of INFORE [20], [21]. This component is able to detect or forecast complex events (i.e., events that are composed of more simple events). An example of a simple event is illegal fishing. A fishing vessel might start moving towards an illegal fishing area, while decreasing also its speed and then switch off each transponder, thus triggering an AIS-off event. In this case, the complex event processing/forecasting component of INFORE will produce an illegal fishing event. When either a simple or a complex event is triggered, then the hybrid robotic network is triggered. The whole INFORE workflow is shown in Fig. 2.

¹<https://akka.io>

The hybrid robotic network, composed of fixed nodes (a thermal and RGB camera placed on-shore) and mobile nodes, two autonomous Wave Glider surface robots [15] equipped with passive sonar sensors, will autonomously operate to produce a significant local view for the INFORE system. The fusion of global and local view heterogeneous streams of data plays a significant role in acquiring a complete picture of the maritime domain. The capability of using multimodal sensors (e.g. optical and acoustic) and to use the robots mobility enable the system to closely investigate potential dark vessels, i.e., vessels that are temporarily not observable by cooperative target sensors such as the Automatic Identification System (AIS) or have switched off the AIS transponder by purpose. The significant alarms for simple and complex events can be communicated to the C2 centre for well-informed actions by the decision-maker. All events produced by the INFORE workflow are finally visualised using the UI of the MSA application. Using this user-friendly web-based visualisation tool, end-users (e.g., VTS officers, port authorities, etc.) will be able to monitor maritime events in real-time.

For further details on the INFORE system we refer to [22].

III. THE GLOBAL VIEW SENSORS

The global view sensor data provide the large scale surveillance context for the local view to improve MSA. In order to achieve this goal, the sensor suite used in INFORE includes the AIS and two imaging satellite sensors for non-cooperative target detection, the SAR on board the European Space Agency (ESA) Sentinel-1 satellite and the MSI sensor on board the ESA-Sentinel-2 satellite. They both provide high resolution images of ship targets, but in different spectral ranges, the microwave and the visible/near-infrared, respectively. The two sensors are complementary as the SAR, in the microwave spectrum, is not affected by the cloud coverage like the MSI. However, the MSI in good atmospheric conditions is able to provide additional details that are useful to identify the target.

The AIS is an automated tracking system that allows the exchange of navigational information between AIS-equipped terminals. Since December 2004, the International Maritime Organisation (IMO) requires all passengers' vessels, as well as, all commercial vessels over 299 Gross Tonnage (GT) that travel internationally to carry a Class A AIS transponder (which transmits and receives AIS data) aboard (smaller vessels can also be equipped with a Class B AIS transponder). AIS transponders (on vessel stations) include a GPS (Global Positioning System) receiver which collects the subject vessel's position and movement details. Such (dynamic) details along with other static information provided by the vessel's crew are automatically broadcasted at regular intervals and received by other vessels or base stations (provided they are within range). The system is primarily used for collision avoidance and traffic monitoring by maritime authorities. Historical data sets are now used to analyze and find traffic patterns and traffic anomalies. Despite the widespread use of AIS and its contribution in raising the maritime awareness and safety of navigation, it comes with some issues such as the intentional switch-off of the transponder by the vessel crew.

Sensors for non-cooperative target detection are then used to avoid, also partially, the issues of the AIS. The SAR and MSI sensors are used to detect ship targets and classify the ship type. In particular, convolutional neural networks (CNN) for target classification are trained by using a data set of target images that are semi-automatically labeled by associating target contacts on the sensor image to AIS target positions. The classifiers achieve a classification accuracy on the test set that is greater than 95% for the MSI [23] (see Fig. III for an example of features extracted by the CNN classifier for classes Cargo, Tanker, Other) and close to 90% in the SAR case. Detected contact positions and classification information are integrated in the MSA fusion engine and used to confirm vessel identities and to spot vessels with AIS transponder that is turned-off.

IV. INFORE HYBRID ROBOTIC NETWORK

The INFORE hybrid robotic network is composed of an onshore RGB and thermal camera and two Liquid Robotics Wave Gliders [11], [12] (see Fig. 1) equipped with passive sonars [13], [24] as mobile sensorised robots. The camera and the robots cooperate for increasing the overall network performance. As shown in Fig. 4, the network is ruled at a high-level by a two states state-machine. The network starts in the *Area survey* state with the assets monitoring a region of interest for detecting and localising vessels which navigate in the area. The INFORE MSA and decision-support platform can inform the network in case some alarms are produced, such as the approach to the surveyed region of a suspicious ship. This can influence the network monitoring operations, for instance the robots modify their routes. If some of the sensors confirm a target of interest, the network switches to the *Target localisation* state. Either the camera or the robots can confirm the target presence triggering the state switching. Information about the target position, speed and features is shared to coordinate the network operations. Robots autonomously navigate to improve the target detection, localisation and tracking, while the camera points at the target estimate location to increase the tracking and classification performance. The produced information about the target are also communicated to the INFORE platform and this helps to generate event detections which raise alarms for the C2 centre decisions.

A. The onshore RGB and thermal camera

Onshore cameras are mainly used for target detection and classification over a given limited area. Visible RGB and thermal cameras are used to have sensor diversity and to improve robustness of the system under different conditions (e.g. environmental

Fig. 3. Example of features of a ship type classifier based on CNN for classes Cargo, Tanker, Other.

Fig. 4. Operative states of the robotics network. If the target is confirmed in the area of interest (either produced by the robots or the camera) the network switches to the target localisation state. In this state, the robots autonomously maneuver to improve target detection and the camera will track the target. Robots and camera share information about the tracked vessel to improve the detection and tracking performance.

and day/night). The approach followed for image segmentation and target classification is again based on the use of convolution neural networks (like in the MSI and SAR cases) for which initial tests on limited data sets provided a classification accuracy of about 80%. The use of robust principal component analysis (RPCA) techniques (see Fig. IV-A) is also experimented in order to accurately separate the fixed background pixels in the video stream and improve the detection of moving targets and subsequent classification steps.

B. The Wave Glider robots equipped with passive sonars

The Wave Glider Fig. 6 is a new class of wave-propelled, persistent ocean vehicle, which is propelled by the conversion of ocean wave energy into forward thrust, independent of wave direction. It is a hybrid sea-surface and underwater vehicle composed of a submerged "glider" attached via a tether to a surface float. The submerged gliders vertical motion through the comparatively still waters at the gliders depth allows its wings to convert a portion of this up-ward motion into a forward propulsion force [25].

CMRE has extensively used Wave Gliders as nodes of its robotics networks [15], due to the locomotion system characterised by low emitted noise and low power consumption. The Wave Gliders, despite their relatively low speed (even if a propeller has been added to the recent model to increase the speed), can therefore operate as silent and long endurance robots acting as

Fig. 5. Example of moving target detection using RPCA. The frame in the video sequence is separated in a low rank background and in a sparse foreground containing the ship target. The detection mask is obtained by applying a threshold to the foreground mask. The graph on the right depicts the histogram of the foreground image with the applied threshold in red.

Fig. 6. Deployment of the SV3 CMRE Wave Glider during DANS20 trial. The Wave Glider is a two-part vehicle, with a submerged glider connected to a surface body. The Wave Glider exploits the wave energy for locomotion and can be equipped with different sensors and payloads. In the case of DANS20, Wave Gliders were equipped with radio communication devices, and towed acoustic modems or an acoustic vector sensor array [26].

mobile communication gateways [6] or as sensing platforms if equipped with passive sonars. For the INFORE network, CMRE has integrated a volumetric acoustic array, the PERSEUS [24], with the robots and has developed a cooperative autonomy framework running onboard the vehicles.

Passive sonar sensor: the PERSEUS volumetric array

The design of the volumetric array developed by CMRE during the PERSEUS FP7 project [24] was used to refit and assemble new sensors for the INFORE Wave Gliders (see Fig. 7). The PERSEUS array is a compact volumetric (3D) array attached to the Wave Glider tow-fish body. The three-dimensional array is designed to be omnidirectional and it consists of 8

Fig. 7. (a) PERSEUS volumetric array towed by a Wave Glider. (b) Results during tests at CMRE water basin on 16 July 2019. A rubber boat equipped with a GPS acted as a target for the PERSEUS sensor. In the figure are reported the direction of arrival computed by the sensor and the groundtruth from GPS.

Fig. 8. CMRE Wave Glider software architecture. With the introduction of the Wave Glider Autonomy Adapter module, the iCADME control autonomy software can now control directly the Wave Glider Frontseat, hence influencing the vehicle navigation. iCADME makes autonomous decisions considered the received information by other network nodes or by the C2 centre and the bearing measurements produced by the acoustic array.

hydrophones positioned in a small triangle of 10 cm long side, included in a sort of squared-basis pyramid. Hydrophones are omnidirectional and pre-amplified; their frequency response, measured in CMRE water tank facility, is linear-phase and flat (± 2 dB) at least below 70 kHz (sensitivity -168 dB re $V/\mu\text{Pa}$ at 10 kHz). All hydrophones data are simultaneously sampled at high frequency (selectable between 100 and 140 kHz) to exploit the wide acoustic bandwidth of the signals of interest and to have high resolution cross-correlation data available from pairs of hydrophones. Either cross-correlation or beamforming can be used to compute the contact direction of arrival.

Fig. 7 shows the results of the PERSEUS characterisation held on 16 July 2019 at the CMRE water basin. A rubber boat moved in front of the sensor acting as a target. In the figure the direction of arrival computed by the PERSEUS array in real-time is shown along with the groundtruth computed using a GPS onboard the rubber boat. The sensor was demonstrated capable of detecting the rubber boat navigation at a speed of about 5 kns with a sufficient precision of its localisation and tracking.

Making the Wave Glider fully autonomous

The traditional control strategy for Wave Gliders relies on an onboard "Frontseat" computer, provided by the manufacturer, which reads the vehicle navigation sensors (e.g. GPS, compass, water speed sensor, etc.) and executes the autopilot navigation algorithms, such as move to waypoint and station-keeping at a certain location, actuating the rudder and possibly the propeller [11], [12]. Even if a radio module is available, the Frontseat computer typically communicates via an Iridium satellite modem [11] with a C2 centre, either located onshore or onboard a support vessel. This control paradigm involves the execution of the autonomy software at the C2 centre and the transmission of the computed commands (e.g. a list of waypoints) to the Frontseat computer via the Iridium link. However, the use of the Iridium link represents a significant barrier to adaptive autonomy, since its limited bandwidth can hinder the data exchange needed for effective autonomous decision in the case of usage of data-intensive sensors (e.g. acoustics).

To address these limitations, CMRE added a so-called "Backseat" computer onboard the vehicle according to the "backseat-driver" paradigm [27], [28], in which a Backseat computer runs the "intelligent" software issuing commands to a Frontseat computer. In the CMRE Wave Glider, the Backseat computer runs the communication stack that manages the networking, [29], or can execute the signal processing chain if a sensor is towed. However, despite some CMRE previous preliminary work [30], the Backseat and Frontseat had not directly been connected.

For developing the INFORE network, we have to execute cooperative autonomy software onboard the Wave Glider Backseat, and enabling it to directly control the Frontseat, hence influencing the vehicle navigation. To this purpose, we have developed the Wave Glider Autonomy Adapter software module [15]. The module interfaces the Backseat autonomy with the Frontseat handling the communication protocol via a serial link. The Backseat can now command waypoints or heading commands to the Wave Glider hardware. The resulting software architecture is shown in Fig. 8. The software executed on the Backseat computer runs in the Mission Oriented Operating Suite (MOOS) robotics software middleware [27], [28] environment. MOOS-IvP is a set of open source C++ modules, built on the publish/subscribe paradigm. The CMRE *intelligent Cooperative Autonomous Decision Making Engine (iCADME)* [29], [31] is used to control the vehicles. iCADME is a three-layer, hybrid [32] cooperative autonomy framework which manages multi-task mission. iCADME can execute tasks, making cooperative decisions and issuing navigation commands to the Wave Glider autopilots through the Autonomy Adapter module. For further details we refer to [15], [29]. It remains to describe the cooperative strategies designed for controlling the Wave Gliders in their mission.

An Occupancy Grid Mapping framework for cooperative autonomy

We have developed an Occupancy Grid (OG) Mapping framework [33] for managing the cooperative area survey and target localisation tasks of the robots [13], [14]. The approach relies on data fusion. Robots exchange bearing-only measurements produced by the passive sonars and the framework fuses them to estimate the latitude/longitude of the target. This is the basis for cooperative decision-making to produce network geometric configurations which improve target detection and tracking.

OG Mapping requires discretisation of the environment into a collection of small cells, each of which is considered as being either completely occupied or completely empty. Let C be the number of cells in an OG map. $m_{1:C}$ denotes the collection of all binary cell states, and $z_{1:t}$ denotes the collection of all measurements. Then, considered as a Bayesian C-dimensional binary estimation problem, all information about the state of the map would be contained in the posterior:

$$p(m_{1:C}|z_{1:t}) \quad (1)$$

Unfortunately, the number of possible maps is 2^C , and so it is usually prohibitive to store or compute this full posterior. Consequently, OG mapping methods typically seek the marginal posteriors for the occupancy of each cell

$$p(m_i|z_{1:t}) \quad (2)$$

Approximations are usually used to allow this computation in real-time [33]. We developed a method based on the so-called IP map update [34], [35] and we introduced a method to handle the dynamic world situation, typical of our applications (vessels move). A scheme of the OG-based cooperative framework is shown in Fig. 9 (see [13], [14] for details). A mathematical sensor model (probability of detection at different bearing/ranges and false alarm rate) is built based on experimental data collected with PERSEUS array (see the Sec. IV-B). Using the model and the map update, each robot builds its own OG map. Produced maps are used to drive the robot area survey. Low occupancy cells (dark blue) are indicative or regions likely empty, while higher occupancy (yellowish in the figure) are related to the possible presence of a target. Maps also indicate regions which have to be further explored. The maps are then fused and the Laplacian operator is applied to the fused map. Low values of the Laplacian are related to the presence of a targets (high peaks in the occupancy probabilities). Maps are then projected into the future considering different robots heading decisions. Robots selects their headings to create geometric configurations characterised by fused maps with low Laplacian values, improving target detection and localisation. After an evaluation of the framework in non-trivial computer simulations, we have been porting the framework in the iCADME control architecture for forthcoming tests at sea.

V. INFORE MSA ONTOLOGY

To model the information requirements of the INFORE MSA platform, we developed a semantic model for maritime linked data, namely the maritime situational awareness - heterogeneous sensor network (MSA-HSN) ontology [36]. MSA-HSN is defined in OWL (Web Ontology Language)² and can be used to semantically annotate and enrich the sensor information flowing into and produced by a typical maritime information fusion system. MSA-HSN maritime linked data offer an effective information support for MSA and maritime security systems, and the proposed model is potentially applicable in a variety of scenarios, like the detection of maritime threats and illegal activities, maritime traffic monitoring, critical infrastructures

²Web Ontology Language (Web Ontology Language): <https://www.w3.org/OWL/>

Fig. 9. Scheme of the developed OG Mapping framework for cooperative autonomy. OG Maps are produced using the bearing measurements onboard each robot. Maps are fused and the Laplacian operator is used to localise likely target positions (low Laplacian values). Maps are projected into the future considering different robot heading decisions. Robots cooperatively selects heading decisions to create network geometric configurations that maximise the possibility to detect and localise a target.

protection, supply chain management, all requiring the fusion of information produced by sources of various reliability and quality.

MSA-HSN extends and adapts existing information models for sensors and observations (the Semantic Sensor Network/ Sensor Observation Sampling Actuator (SSN/ SOSA) [37]), data streams (the IoT-Stream [38]), measures and units (the Ontology units of Measures (OM) [39]), and events (the Simple Event Model (SEM) [40]). MSA-HSN also leverages the Common information Sharing Environment (CISE) data model [41] for maritime events and data modelling and integrations proposed by recent border protection European projects (e.g., Andromeda [42] and ROBORDER [41]).

MSA-HSN seamlessly models sensor signals, observations and derived information like detection contacts or complex analytics, detected and forecasted maritime events or anomalies and maritime activities. The base sensor and observation model is further extended to support information aspects crucial for MSA applications, like data provenance and information quality which need to be evaluated by the information fusion system. Sensor values and streams can be of any nature (quantitative, multi-granular spatio-temporal, and qualitative). Leveraging the categories defined in [41] qualitative aspects of information, which are needed by the information fusion system to correctly combine the sensor signals, are integrated. The uncertainty of observations and analytics is modelled explicitly and linked to the originating data and to the originating sensors.

The modelling of maritime events and anomalies relies on the Simple event model [40], as adopted in [41]. It has been extended to include the representation of the event context, constructed on the basis of the profiles of the entities observed by sensors and specifically modelled for supporting situation awareness and threat assessment in surveillance applications [43].

The MSA-HSN supports the semantic annotation and enrichment of the information flowing into the INFORE MSA platform, but it is designed to be in line with the requirements of any information fusion systems applied to MSA use cases.

VI. A TYPICAL SCENARIO

To better describe how the INFORE MSA system works in combining global and local views, we present an illegal fishing scenarios, that is one of the scenarios we will address within our maritime use case. A map and description of the scenario is reported in Fig. 10. The sea region shown is off the coasts of Palmaria island, close to La Spezia, Italy. The area inside the red rectangle represents a protected sea area where fishing is prohibited. A ship is navigating towards south-east. Ship's AIS data are monitored by the INFORE system. At a certain time, the ship turns to east and switches its AIS off. The INFORE

Fig. 10. Description of an illegal fishing scenario in a protected area (inside the red rectangle). The ship will turn its AIS off and will head to the protected area, starting to loglining. The Wave Gliders, triggered by the INFORE system, will cooperate to estimate the vessel position and feed it into the INFORE MSA and decision-support platform, which will finally detect an illegal fishing complex event.

event detector (see Fig. 2) reports a simple event (the ship approaching the protected areas) to the hybrid robotic network. This triggers the Wave Gliders and the camera which start monitoring the location transmitted by the INFORE MSA and decision-support platform. Wave Gliders then detect the vessel and cooperatively navigate to estimate the ship’s position. This information is provided to the INFORE system that can finally recognise a fishing activity raising an alarm related to this complex event. This kind of scenarios will be tested in non-trivial simulations involving Marine Traffic and CMRE and will be the basis for the final system trials that will be held in 2022.

VII. CONCLUSION

We described the MSA system developed in the framework of the INFORE EU H2020 project. INFORE has the objective of developing a real-time, interactive extreme-scale analytics and forecasting system capable of handling and analysing massive data streams. The MSA use case we described in this paper is one of the three real-world use cases on which the INFORE system is validated. The MSA INFORE system aims at improving coastal surveillance exploiting the synergy between global view (AIS data, MSI and SAR Sentinel data), which observes a wider area and provides contextual information, and local view produced by a sensorised hybrid robotic network. The network is composed of a RGB/thermal camera onshore and of two Wave Gliders robots equipped with passive sonars. Global and local views are fused by the INFORE MSA and decision-support platform using machine learning classification algorithms for supporting decision-makers. The INFORE MSA network demonstrates the benefits that the synergy between machine learning, AI and autonomous robots can bring in this coastal surveillance systems.

In this paper, after a general description of the MSA INFORE system, we focused on the development of the hybrid robotic network, detailing the OG-based cooperative autonomy framework which controls the Wave Glider robots. Autonomy of the robots is crucial for enabling the network to adapt its geometry for searching for configurations favourable for vessel detection and tracking. Data fusion between the bearing measurements produced onboard the robots is used for estimating the target position. The network capability to autonomously make decision increases the quality of the local view, improving complex event detection by INFORE MSA platform. At the same time, autonomy reduces the complexity of robot control from a C2. This increases the system scalability, paving the way to increase the number of network nodes. Different modules of the systems are ready and under testing. The cooperative autonomy framework will be tested during REPMUS21 trial in Portugal in September 2021. The whole system will be validated in a trial in 2022.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors kindly thank Alessandra Tesei, the Scientist in Charge of DANS20 trial, the CMRE engineers, in particular Alberto Grati and Stefano Biagini, for their support, and the officers and crew of the NRV Alliance.

REFERENCES

- [1] E. Martineau and J. Roy, “Maritime anomaly detection: Domain introduction and review of selected literature,” 2011.
- [2] Integrated Maritime Policy of the European Union. [Online]. Available: <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/factsheets/en/sheet/121/the-integrated-maritime-policy>
- [3] Department of the Navy (United States of America), “TheNavy unmanned undersea vehicle (UUV) master plan,” Tech. Rep., 2004.
- [4] C. C. Eriksen, T. J. Osse, R. D. Light, T. Wen, T. W. Lehman, P. L. Sabin, J. W. Ballard, and A. M. Chiodi, “Seaglider: a long-range autonomous underwater vehicle for oceanographic research,” *IEEE Journal of Oceanic Engineering*, vol. vol. 26., no. no. 4, pp. 424–436, 2001.
- [5] T. Fossum, “Intelligent autonomous underwater vehicles,” Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Tech. Rep., 2016.
- [6] G. Ferri, A. Munafò, A. Tesei, P. Braca, F. Meyer, K. Pelekanakis, R. Petroccia, J. Alves, C. Strode, and K. LePage, “Cooperative robotic networks for underwater surveillance: an overview,” *IET Radar, Sonar & Navigation. Special Issue: Sonar multi-sensor applications and techniques*, vol. 11, no. 12, pp. 1740 – 1761, 2017.

Fig. 11. Example of a simulation with robots controlled by the cooperative target localisation algorithm and Laplacian of the fused map. A target is present following a typical longlining fishing patterns (see [22]). Robot 1 position is represented with a black circle and the current heading with a segment originated from the robot location. The sensor footprint is shown as two black lines that delimit the sensor footprint. The sensor endfire is located at front/back of the robot, and we assume $P_d = 0$ in that area. Bearing measurements of the real target are indicated by a black cross, while triangles indicate bearing measurements due to false alarms. The same quantities are indicated in red for robot 2. The number between the robot indicates their distance in meters. A green diamond indicates the target, while a green square indicates the estimated target position (at the current UT) for robot 1. New measurements are produced periodically at every Update Time (UT) (5 s).

Situation at $UT = 20$ (a), Situation at $UT = 40$ (b), Situation at $UT = 110$ (c): Laplacian LP of the map produced by fusing the single robot maps. In the figure black/red circles of different size in front of the robots represent the considered possible headings. The size is relative to the value of the minimum Laplacian of the expected fused map (larger circle means a lower Laplacian). The last robot decision is marked with a larger black/red hollow circle.

- [7] G. Ferri, A. Munafò, and K. D. LePage, "An Autonomous Underwater Vehicle data-driven control strategy for target tracking," *IEEE Journal of Oceanic Engineering*, vol. Volume: 43, no. Issue: 2, pp. 323 – 343, April 2018.
- [8] S. Topal, I. Erkmen, and A. Erkmen, "Towards the robotic avatar: An extensive survey of the cooperation between and within networked mobile sensors," *Future Internet*, 2010.
- [9] Infore project. [Online]. Available: www.infore-project.eu.
- [10] K. Bereta, D. Zissis, and R. Grasso, "Automatic maritime object detection using satellite imagery," in *GLOBAL OCEANS 2020*, 2020.
- [11] R. Hine, S. Willcox, G. Hine, and T. Richardson, "The Wave Glider: A wave-powered autonomous marine vehicle," in *OCEANS 2009*, 2009.
- [12] J. Manley and S. Willcox, "The wave glider: A persistent platform for ocean science," in *OCEANS'10 IEEE SYDNEY*, 2010.
- [13] G. Ferri, A. Tesei, P. Stinco, and K. D. LePage, "A Bayesian Occupancy Grid Mapping method for the control of passive sonar robotics surveillance networks," in *OCEANS 2019, Marseille (France)*, 2019.
- [14] G. Ferri, P. Stinco, A. Tesei, and K. LePage, "An AUV cooperative target localisation strategy with bearing-only measurements based on Bayesian occupancy grid mapping," in *Global Oceans 2020: Singapore U.S. Gulf Coast*, 2020, pp. 1–8.
- [15] G. Ferri, C. Cesar, A. Faggiani, and K. LePage, "Making a Liquid Robotics Wave Glider fully autonomous: Field results from DANS20 trial," in *Global OCEANS 21*, 2021.
- [16] I. T. Union, "Technical characteristics for an automatic identification system using time division multiple access in the VHF maritime mobile band," International Telecommunications Union, Tech. Rep. ITU-R M.1371-5, 02, Tech. Rep., 2014.
- [17] A. Kontaxakis, N. Giatrakos, and A. Deligiannakis, "A synopsis data engine for interactive extreme-scale analytics," in *CIKM '20: The 29th ACM International Conference on Information and Knowledge Management, Virtual Event, Ireland, October 19-23, 2020*, M. d'Aquin, S. Dietze, C. Hauff, E. Curry, and P. Cudré-Mauroux, Eds. ACM, 2020, pp. 2085–2088.

- [18] D. Zissis, K. Chatzikokolakis, G. Spiliopoulos, and M. Vodas, "A distributed spatial method for modeling maritime routes," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 47 556–47 568, 2020.
- [19] I. Kontopoulos, K. Chatzikokolakis, K. Tserpes, and D. Zissis, "Classification of vessel activity in streaming data," in *DEBS '20: The 14th ACM International Conference on Distributed and Event-based Systems, Montreal, Quebec, Canada, July 13-17, 2020*, J. Gascon-Samson, K. Zhang, K. Daudjee, and B. Kemme, Eds. ACM, 2020, pp. 153–164.
- [20] E. Alevizos, A. Artikis, and G. Paliouras, "Event forecasting with pattern markov chains," in *DEBS*. ACM, 2017, pp. 146–157.
- [21] —, "Wayeb: a tool for complex event forecasting," in *LPAR*, ser. EPiC Series in Computing, vol. 57. EasyChair, 2018, pp. 26–35.
- [22] R. Grasso, G. Ferri, E. Camossi, A. Faggiani, D. Zissis, K. Bereta, K. Chatzikokolakis, I. Kontopoulos, and M. Vodas, "Initial evaluation and validation report," INFORE project, Deliverable D3.2, Tech. Rep., 2021.
- [23] R. Grasso, "Ship classification from multi-spectral satellite imaging by convolutional neural networks," in *27th European Signal Processing Conference, EUSIPCO 2019, A Coruña, Spain, September 2-6, 2019*. IEEE, 2019, pp. 1–5. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.23919/EUSIPCO.2019.8902822>
- [24] A. Tesei, R. Been, D. Williams, B. Carreira, D. Galletti, D. Cecchi, B. Garau, and A. Maguer, "Passive acoustic surveillance of surface vessels using tridimensional array on an underwater glider," in *OCEANS 2015 - Genova*, May 2015, pp. 1–8.
- [25] [Online]. Available: <https://www.liquid-robotics.com/wave-glider/how-it-works/>
- [26] P. Stinco, A. Tesei, G. Ferri, S. Biagini, M. Micheli, B. Garau, K. D. LePage, L. Troiano, A. Grati, and P. Guerrini, "Passive acoustic signal processing at low frequency with a 3-d acoustic vector sensor hosted on a buoyancy glider," *IEEE Journal of Oceanic Engineering*, vol. 46, no. 1, pp. 283–293, 2021.
- [27] M. Benjamin, H. Schmidt, P. Newman, and J. Leonard, "Nested autonomy for unmanned marine vehicles with MOOS-IvP," *Journal of Field Robotics*, no. 27, pp. 834–875, 2010.
- [28] <http://oceanai.mit.edu/moos-ivp/pmwiki/pmwiki.php>.
- [29] G. Ferri, P. Stinco, G. De Magistris, A. Tesei, and K. D. LePage, "Cooperative autonomy and data fusion for underwater surveillance with networked auvs," in *2020 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, 2020, pp. 871–877.
- [30] A. Munafò, J. Sliwka, and J. Alves, "Dynamic placement of a constellation of surface buoys for enhanced underwater positioning," in *OCEANS 2015, Genova, 18-21 May*, 2015.
- [31] G. Ferri, R. Petroccia, G. D. Magistris, L. Morlando, M. Micheli, A. Tesei, and K. LePage, "Cooperative autonomy in the CMRE ASW multistatic robotic network: Results from LCAS18," in *OCEANS19, Marseille (FR)*, 2019.
- [32] R. Murphy, *Introduction to AI robotics*. MIT Press, 2000.
- [33] S. Thrun, W. Burgard, and D. Fox, *Probabilistic robotics*. The MIT Press, 2005.
- [34] M. Jakuba, "Stochastic mapping for chemical plume source localization with application to hydrothermal vent discovery," Ph.D. dissertation, WHOI-MIT, 2007.
- [35] G. Ferri, M. Jakuba, A. Mondini, V. Mattoli, B. Mazzolai, D. Yoerger, and P. Dario, "Mapping multiple gas/odor sources in an uncontrolled indoor environment using a bayesian occupancy grid mapping based method," *Robotics and Autonomous Systems* 59 (11), pp. 968–1000, 2011.
- [36] E. Camossi, R. Grasso, G. Ferri, A. Faggiani, K. LePage, and S. Carniel, "Maritime linked data for situational awareness heterogeneous sensor networks (to appear)," in *OCEANS 2021*, 2021.
- [37] Armin Haller et al., "The Modular SSN Ontology: A Joint W3C and OGC Standard Specifying the Semantics of Sensors, Observations, Sampling, and Actuation," *Semantic Web*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 9–32, 2019.
- [38] Tarek Elsaleh et al., "Iot-stream: A lightweight ontology for internet of things data streams and its use with data analytics and event detection services." *Sensors (Basel)*, vol. 20, no. 4, p. 953, Feb 2020.
- [39] Hajo Rijgersberg et al., "Ontology of units of measure and related concepts," *Semantic Web Journal*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 3–13, 2013.
- [40] van Hage, W. R. et al., "Design and use of the Simple Event Model (SEM)," *J. of Web Semantics*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 128–136, July 2011.
- [41] Marina Riga et al., "EUCISE-OWL: An Ontology-based Representation of the Common Information Sharing Environment (CISE) for the Maritime Domain," *Semantic Web*, 2019.
- [42] S. Antonopoulos, M. Tsogas, M. Moutzouris, A. Kostaridis, A. Aggelis, and L. Perlepes, "D.3.1 e-cise data model description."
- [43] E. Camossi and F. de Rosa, "Semantic-driven modelling of context and entity of interest profiles for maritime situation awareness," in *Proceedings of the Joint Ontology Workshops co-located with the Bolzano Summer of Knowledge (BOSK 2020)*, 2020. [Online]. Available: <http://ceur-ws.org/Vol-2708/womocoe1.pdf>